

any injury attributable to pathogens was found either, except for ShB, whose injury was also increased by fungicide use. Relationships between different cropping practices (e.g., water management, variety, etc.) did not show a distinctive pattern. A multivariate approach was then used to address multiple, complex associations.

Results of chi square tests and multiple correspondence analysis can be summarized as follows:

Winter-spring was characterized by higher levels of LB, RS, and BPH; summer by higher RS and WA; and autumn by higher BLB and BS, but lower levels of RS. ShB injury, high in all seasons, peaked in winter-spring.

In winter-spring, water management was generally good; in summer, water stress was found in some fields, and there were low fertilizer inputs and higher use of herbicides; in autumn, water excess (floods) occurred in some fields.

Winter-spring was characterized by higher yields (5 t ha⁻¹ and more), summer by medium yields (2.5-5 t ha⁻¹, and autumn by low yields (2.5 t ha⁻¹ and less).

Multiple correspondence analysis using patterns of cropping practices and injury variables described much of the yield variation: at least 88% of each yield class is accounted for on the first two

Variation in levels of injuries with rice cropping seasons. Can Tho Province, Mekong Delta. 1996.

Injury ^a	Winter-spring (Dec-Mar)	Summer (Apr-Jul)	Autumn (Jul-Oct)	F	P
Leafhopper ^b	517	118	9	32.2	<0.001
Whiteheads ^c	0.19	0.38	0.51	0.80	0.45
Deadhearts ^c	2.50	1.00	0.90	4.69	0.01
Weed below the rice canopy ^d	170	400	414	2.74	0.07
Weed above the rice canopy ^d	385	600	232	4.56	0.01
Neck blast ^c	2.83	1.17	0.36	1.98	0.14
Stem rot ^c	0.75	0.21	0.12	2.72	0.07
Sheath rot ^c	0.77	7.41	1.84	4.96	0.01
Sheath blight ^c	3.28	4.07	9.22	3.32	0.04
Red stripe ^b	352	228	135	4.67	0.01
Brown spot ^b	649	583	1885	17.3	<0.001
Leaf blast ^b	253	5	3	18.0	<0.001
Bacterial blight ^b	21	16	195	4.38	0.01
Rice bugs ^e	0.35	0.33	3.08	2.58	0.08
Brown planthopper ^e	75	28	10	9.70	<0.001

^aInjury levels are indicated in different units. The magnitude of entries does not reflect the magnitude of the injurious effect on the crop and the yield-reducing effects. ^bArea under progress curve of mean proportion of injured leaves. ^cMaximum proportion of tillers injured over four successive visits. ^dArea under progress curve of proportion of soil covered by weed canopy. ^eArea under progress curve of mean insect catches over four successive visits.

combined axes. (These axes represent independent combinations of variables, except yield, using a chi-square distance.)

This analysis indicates no apparent effect of pesticide use—fungicides, insecticides, and herbicides—on the pattern of distribution of injuries. In other words, pesticides do not appear to have any significant effect on the overall occurrence of pests, except for the two cases mentioned.

This survey provides a first overview of injuries due to pests in Mekong Delta rice cultivation. It points to sea-

sonal patterns, a few environmental factors that may influence injuries, and some links among injuries. The survey results permit us to make hypotheses, especially to explain why pesticide use, which is very high, has so little effect on injury levels, and hypotheses about red stripe syndrome. Surveys in the Mekong Delta are ongoing. We expect to derive from an additional year of survey—and a larger survey data set—production situations (combination of climatic and crop management practices) that will permit us to develop testable hypotheses. ■

Integrated pest management—insects

Impact of methyl parathion on the natural enemies of rice insect pests in Cambodia

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Methyl parathion is one of the most commonly used insecticides in Cambodia. An experiment at Kap Srau Station, Phnom Penh, during 1994 main crop season evaluated methyl parathion effects on major arthropod groups in rainfed lowland rice.

We planted IR72 in a randomized complete block design on 35- × 20-m plots, with treatments of sprayed and unsprayed plots each replicated three times. Methyl parathion was sprayed 14 and 38 d after transplanting (DT) at 0.75 kg ai ha⁻¹. Arthropods were sampled 1 d before (DBS) and at 3 d after spraying (DAS). Samples were taken from 10 randomly selected sites per plot using a blower-vac suction machine. Each sample site was enclosed with a bottomless plastic bucket fixed with a muslin cloth around its

opening to prevent escape of arthropods during suction. The enclosed area was 0.102 m² and covered 3-4 hills. Arthropods were placed in labeled vials with 80% alcohol, counted, and identified. Damage from defoliators was also recorded at 45 DT from 10 randomly selected hills plot⁻¹. Yields were taken from 2- × 5-m area in each plot and adjusted to 14% moisture content.

The arthropod population collected at the first set of samplings was too low for useful comparisons. In the second sampling, green leafhopper density

N. virescens (no. enclosure⁻¹)

Gonatocerus sp. (no. enclosure⁻¹)

Spiders (no. enclosure⁻¹)

Cyrtorhinus sp. (no. enclosure⁻¹)

Microvelia (no. enclosure⁻¹)

Collembola (no. enclosure⁻¹)

2. Population of common predators of insect pests of rice and collembolans 1DBS and 3 d DAS. Kap Srau, Phnom Penh, Cambodia, 1994 wet season.

increased in both treated and untreated plots by 3 DAS (42 DT). By contrast, the number of *Gonatocerus* spp., an egg parasitoid of *Nephotettix virescens*, declined (Fig. 1). Populations of spiders and collembolans were heavily affected by insecticide applications. The spraying had no effect on the populations of *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* Reuter and *Microvelia douglasi atrolineata* Bergorth (Fig. 2). Leaf damage was similar (15 and 16%) and yield comparable (2970 ±

209 and 2290 ± 221 kg ha⁻¹) in the treated and untreated plots. The insecticide did not appear to cause significant reduction in pest species and predators such as *Cyrtorhinus* and *Microvelia*. Instead, it had more significant effects on parasitoids, spiders, and collembolans.

It is likely that pest infestations in Cambodia are inherently low, especially in an insect-resistant cultivar like IR72. Methyl parathion applications are thus not justified. ■

Effect of soil amendments on grain yield and incidence of rice leaffolder in iron-toxic soils of north Orissa, India

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In valley areas of north Orissa, India, the incidence of rice leaffolder (LF), *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*, and iron toxicity have been of concern in wetland rice production. This field experiment examined the effects of soil amendments on the incidence of LF and the grain yield of two varieties, Lalat and Jajati.

A factorial randomized block design with three replications was laid out in farmers' fields adjacent to the iron ore mines of Joda, Keonjhar (Orissa), India. The soil (Oxic Paleustalf) of the experiment site had a pH of 4.8. The HCl extract of the soil evidenced Fe²⁺ content of 3500 ppm (by ortho phenanthroline method). The treatments consisted of application of various fertilizer rates with organic manure as amendments on 12 × 12-m plots. One-month-old seedlings were transplanted at a spacing of 15 × 10 cm on 24 Jul 1993. The percentage of leaf damage caused by the LF in each plot was ascertained at the flag leaf stage by counting the total and infested leaves on 10 random-

Table 1. Leaffolder (LF) incidence and grain yield in response to amendments to iron-toxic soils in rice, irrespective of variety.

Treatment	Leaf damage (%) by LF ^a	Grain yield (tha ⁻¹)
60:13.2:24.9 kg NPK ha ⁻¹	22.6 (27.2)	2.7
T ₁ + cowdung @ 5 t ha ⁻¹	34.6 (35.8)	3.4
T ₁ + MnO (4%) seedling root dip	32.6 (34.7)	2.9
60:13.2:49.8 kg NPK ha ⁻¹	22.6 (28.3)	2.9
60:13.2:74.7 kg NPK ha ⁻¹	25.3 (30.1)	3.0
60:13.2:99.6 kg NPK ha ⁻¹	22.6 (28.1)	2.9
30:13.2:24.9 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + FYM @ 3.3 t ha ⁻¹ + green leaves of <i>Ipomoea</i> @ 1.7 t ha ⁻¹	25.3 (29.9)	2.8
LSD (P=0.05)	3.8	ns ^b

^a Figures in parentheses are in corresponding angular values.

^b ns = not significant.